

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1. Analytical methods for environmental variables considered as predictors in the base-models for the meiofauna descriptors.

Variables	Analytic method	Reference
Chlorophyll - a ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Spectrophotometric method proposed by Lorenzen (1967). The freeze-dried sediments were weighed into a Falcon tube ($1.0 \text{ g} \pm 0.010 \text{ g}$) and 10 mL of 90% acetone was added. The tubes were vigorously shaken with a vortex, ultrasonicated for 3 minutes and stored overnight at 4 °C in the dark. Tubes were then centrifuged (3000 rpm for 10 minutes) and the absorbance of the supernatant was measured at the wavelengths of 750 and 665 nm against a blank of 90% acetone. For phaeopigment determination, the acetone extract was acidified directly in the cuvette with 2 drops of 0.1 N HCl and the absorbance was measured again at 750 and 665 nm. The chlorophyll-a and phaeopigments contents were calculated according to Lorenzen (1967).	Carreira et al. 2022
Phaeopigments ($\mu\text{g/g}$)		
Chl.a/Phaeo ($\mu\text{g/g}$)		
Total Organic Content (mg/g)	Elemental analyzer equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (Flash 2000 model OEA) coupled to an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Delta V 102 IRMS, Thermo).	Carreira et al. 2022
Nitrogen (molar)		
Carbon/Nitrogen (molar)		
$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰)		
$\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (‰)		
Organic Phosphorus ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Digestion and spectrophotometric method (Aspila et al., 1976). For the total phosphorus determination, an aliquot ($0.5 \text{ to } 1.5 \text{ g} \pm 0.1 \text{ g}$) of freeze-dried sediments were combusted in a muffle furnace at 550 °C for 2h, followed by extraction of the residue with 1 M HCl during 12h at room temperature. After centrifugation (3000 rpm for 10 min), 2 mL of the supernatant were diluted with water to 50 mL and a blue complex with molybdenum was developed for spectrophotometric determination at 800 nm. The concentration of P-PO ₄ , in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, was calculated based on a calibration curve of a potassium dihydrogen phosphate [KH ₂ PO ₄] solution. The inorganic phosphorus was determined in another sediment aliquot following the same procedure for total phosphorus, excluding the thermal treatment. The organic phosphorus was calculated by the difference between total and inorganic phosphorus.	Carreira et al. 2022
Inorganic Phosphorus ($\mu\text{g/g}$)		
Total Phosphorus ($\mu\text{g/g}$)		
Carbohydrates (mgC/g)	Colorimetric assay optimized based on the reaction between sugars and phenol in the presence of concentrated sulfuric acid (Danovaro, 2010). Absorbances were determined by spectrophotometry at 485 and 600 nm and results quantified in D-glucose equivalents by calibration curve.	Carreira et al. 2022
Proteins (mg/g)	Colorimetric method proposed by Bradford (1976) and Hartree (1972), modified by Rice (1982).	Carreira et al. 2022
Lipids (mg/g)	Determined by spectrophotometry at 375 nm and quantified through a calibration curve of tripalmitine equivalents (Danovaro, 2010).	Carreira et al. 2022
Biopolymeric Carbon (mg/g)	Sum of the carbon equivalents of the three main biochemical classes of organic compounds; carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids (conversion coefficients were 0.40, 0.49 and 0.75 $\mu\text{g C } \mu\text{g}^{-1}$, respectively).	Carreira et al. 2022
Granulometric analysis	Percentage of each grain size class was measured with a Laser granulometer, without carbonates extraction.	Figueiredo et al. 2022
Carbonates (%)	Calculated by weight loss in sediment before and after treatment with HCl.	Figueiredo et al. 2022

Supplementary Table 2. Minimum, maximum and mean values for all environmental variables considered as predictors in the base-models for the meiofauna descriptors.

Environmental Variables	Abbreviations	min	max	mean
Water Depth (m)	Depth	24	2447	887.14
Longitude (decimal)	Long	-48.5338	-41.3521	-44.5717
Latitude (decimal)	Lat	-27.538	-22.9477	-25.1615
Chlorophyll - a ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Chl.a	0	4.18	0.682
Phaeopigments ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Phaeo	0.15	33.85	4.89
Chl.a/Phaeo ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Chl.a_Phaeo	0	1.10	0.21
Total Organic Content (mg/g)	TOC	0.31	15.54	6.53
Nitrogen (molar)	N	0	2.68	0.97
Carbon/Nitrogen (molar)	CN	0	12.69	6.51
$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰)	C13	-24.81	-19.85	-21.41
$\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (‰)	N15	0	11.92	6.58
Organic Phosphorus ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	P_Org	0	13.42	4.83
Inorganic Phosphorus ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	P_Inorg	0	11.30	3.98
Total Phosphorus ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	P_Tot	0	17.93	8.79
Carbohydrates (mgC/g)	CHO	0.02	4.01	1.25
Proteins (mg/g)	PRT	0.03	2.85	1.02
PRT/CHO	PRT_CHO	0.19	6.27	1.11
Lipids (mg/g)	LIP	0.03	1.69	0.319
Biopolymeric Carbon (mg/g)	CBP	0.14	6.38	2.59
CBP/TOC	CBP_TOC	0.17	1.17	0.41
Median Grain Size (mm)	Med_Sed	3.50	1242.81	135.17
Mean Grain Size (mm)	Mean_Sed	3.21	1212.96	112.11
Grain Sizes Standard Deviation (mm)	SD_Sed	1.41	13.62	5.44
Total Sand (%)	Sand_tot	0.01	1	0.44
Total Mud (%)	Mud_Tot	0	0.99	0.55
Very Fine Gravel (%)	VF_Gravel	0	0.18	0.02
Very Coarse Sand (%)	VC_Sand	0	0.66	0.06
Coarse Sand (%)	C_Sand	0	0.55	0.08
Medium Sand (%)	M_Sand	0	0.65	0.08
Fine Sand (%)	F_Sand	0	0.64	0.10
Very Fine Sand (%)	VF_Sand	0	0.56	0.12

Very Coarse Silt (%)	VC_Silt	0	0.28	0.09
Coarse Silt (%)	C_Silt	0	0.17	0.08
Medium Silt (%)	M_Silt	0	0.25	0.10
Fine Silt (%)	F_Silt	0	0.32	0.11
Very Fine Silt (%)	VF_Silt	0	0.28	0.09
Clay (%)	Clay	0	0.27	0.07
Carbonates (%)	Carbonates	0.01	0.87	0.36